

Supplementary Figure 4. Phenotypic stability of C9 over 20 culture passages. Flow cytometric analysis at (A) P2 and (B) P20 quantifying expression of CD34, PDGFR α , CXCR4, PDGFR β , c-kit, CD31, CD146, NG2 in C9 PICs.